

Low Cost Sewage Monitoring System Using IoT in Smart Cities

Ajay R^{#1}, Manu Gowda S H^{#2}, Poornima V B^{#3}, Vaibhav S^{#4}, Sudha L K^{#5}

Department of Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering, Bangalore Institute of Technology, Karnataka, India

Abstract—Sewage monitoring and management is one of the most common and important domains, especially in big cities, where population density is more. Hence, monitoring of these sewage systems is an important and necessary task of the municipal authorities of the city as leakage of the sewage water has many adverse effects on the health of the living beings like spreading of various communicable and non-communicable diseases, inhaling problems due to the poisonous gasses, etc. The above problems can be addressed by using smart sewage monitoring systems using Internet of Things technology. This research work proposes a comprehensive solution for monitoring sewage systems using an array of sensors and cloud-based software through Wi-Fi. The core component is an ultrasonic sensor that tracks sewage levels within manholes, interfacing with a TCP/UDP cloud platform and Microcontroller ESP32 via Wi-Fi connection. When the sewage level exceeds a predefined threshold, alerts are triggered through a mobile application or email notifications. The additional sensors for water flow, gas presence, pH levels, and temperature provide supplementary data for monitoring and analysis. The real time practical implementation involves mounting of the sensors on manhole lids, with data relayed to a control room or monitoring interface via the cloud platform. A buzzer adds an auditory alert system for critical situations such as sewage overflow or hazardous gas detection. The system architecture allows for scalability, with the potential to replicate and deploy across multiple locations at lower cost. Overall, this work offers a robust solution for real-time sewage monitoring, alerting, and data analysis through Internet of Things to ensure efficient management and timely response to potential issues at less time and lower cost in smart cities.

Keywords - ESP32, Gas sensor, Internet of Things, pH sensor, Ultrasonic sensor, Sewage systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Daniel Granlund, Robert Brännström Pervasive and Mobile Computing Luleå University of Technology Skellefteå, Sweden, 2012 [1] and the title is Smart City: The Smart Sewerage. This paper introduces a sewerage monitoring system developed in response to a cryptosporidiosis outbreak in Skellefteå in 2011. It explores the technological and political aspects of implementing a smart city sewerage solution, emphasizing continuous monitoring for fast detection of leaks and floods. The paper concludes by highlighting the system's readiness for production and its contribution to sustainable urban development. One major limitation of this paper is its predominantly technical focus, which overlooks the broader socio-economic and regulatory challenges inherent in implementing smart sewerage systems within complex urban environments “Yves Abou Rjeily, Marwan Sadek, Fadi Hage Chehade” [2] Smart system for urban sewage: Feedback on the use of smart sensors. This paper presents a comprehensive examination of the utilization of smart sensor technology to monitor and analyze both storm water and wastewater networks at the Scientific Campus of the University of Lille in France. With the campus representing a town of approximately 25,000 users, the study offers insights into the monitoring systems deployed, data analysis methodologies employed, and the resulting enhancements in understanding network functioning and performance improvements. Through real-time monitoring strategies facilitated by smart sensors and Automatic Meter Reading (AMR), the paper highlights how proactive management strategies can be developed based on dynamic data insights, aiding in the effective management of urban drainage systems. A major limitation lies in its focus on a single case study—the Scientific Campus of the University of Lille. Smart Sewage Management System 2021 [3]. This paper addresses the pressing issue of sewage management in India, particularly focusing on the risks faced by sanitation workers and the need for innovative solutions to ensure their safety. It proposes the development of a device to monitor the health parameters of workers entering sewage, aiming to mitigate the dangers associated with manual cleaning. Additionally, the paper [4] discusses the transformation of sewage systems into useful water systems, highlighting the importance of automation and advanced technologies such as flow sensors and GSM technology in improving wastewater management. Through a comprehensive literature survey and detailed methodology, the paper outlines the implementation of a semi-automated sewage cleaning system, emphasizing the potential of such solutions to enhance efficiency and reduce health risks. One significant limitation of this paper is the lack of detailed discussion or validation of the proposed device and system for monitoring the health parameters of workers entering sewage. While the concept is presented, there is insufficient information provided on the technological feasibility, practical implementation, or effectiveness of the proposed solution. Additionally, the paper [5]-[7] does not address potential challenges or barriers to deployment, such as regulatory approvals, infrastructure requirements, or cost considerations. Untreated sewage is the leading polluter of water sources in India, causing a host of diseases including diarrhoea, agricultural contamination, and environmental degradation [8]-[10]. The urban poor often live alongside dirty drains and canals in which mosquitoes and germs breed. India's largest cities have centralized sewage systems, complete with underground pipes, pumping stations, and treatment plants [11]. However, these systems are expensive to build and to operate, requiring uninterrupted power, skilled operators, and extensive maintenance. As a result, according to India's Central Pollution Control Board, fewer than half of them work effectively [12]. India's smaller towns cannot afford to build such systems. The good news is that a handful of organizations are developing sewage systems that are less expensive and more effective. [13] Improper sewage disposal as a problem has existed since prehistoric ages, to put it plainly, it is a problem that started the minute, mankind moved indoors. In a country such as India where land is of pivotal

importance, sewage disposal can pose a lot of serious issues, hence something has to be done to prevent it from doing any more damage. The problem of improper sewage disposal has caused many problems such as bacterial infections, water borne diseases, new variants of already existing diseases while also having the possibility of inflicting new kinds of diseases. This becomes almost 100 times more deadly when medical waste mixes with the existing sewage due to some mistake and results many problem to the nature and for humans. [14] These problems cause threats to biodiversity, climate change, soil pollution, water pollution and air pollution and a bunch of other unforeseen problems. Also manhole related deaths have been a cause for concern in recent times and we aim to reduce this with our work.

According to the Global Health Observatory data (WHO), in 1950 about 30 percent of the total world population lived at urban places, which is increased up to 54 percent in 2015 and it will be 60 percent in 2030 with respect to global population. Due to such continuous rural to urban migration process creates overburden on the available city sewage system. The Industrialization, employment opportunity, facility of basic services and amenities, higher standard of the social well-being etc. are the major causes of the rapid urbanization [15]. Addition to this, the higher educational facility, central business district, centers of larger manufacture, health and transportation facilities etc. are the pulling factors for the same. Moreover, the detail map of the urban places showing that, somehow the major sites having higher distribution and density of the population i.e., old core zone of the city, location of the slum zone, major economic services etc. Such highly populated areas become the major vulnerable zones for the crises of urban sewage system.

Sewage is one of the important infrastructure in the expanding city that citizen expect to function properly [16]. Sewage management also one of the parameter which measures the developed stage of the residing area, measured based on proper sewage disposal and management. To maintain a sustainable growth of cities, the use of sensors and Internet of Things (IoT) are natural building blocks. With no proper Sewage monitoring and management technique, there would be a wide spread of a number of disease. Sewage management is an important aspect of municipal infrastructure and undoubtedly, it affects our daily hygiene. Poor sewage/drainage management can cause urban floods which is most common in crowded cities. The main objective of this project is to investigate the technological possibilities to build a smart city, and to implement a prototype system in order to avoid situation as describe above [17]. The proposed system monitors the level of sewage in the man-hole, detects a emission of poisonous gas emitting out of sewage, monitors Temperature of sewage water, records ph, measures the flow rate and flooding detection or leakage detection which help us to take up quick response and actions. [18] Low-cost, real-time monitoring and overflow detection with notification alerts is one of the key features of our project which is very much necessary in the present day.

II. EXISTING SYSTEM

Fig.1 shows the block diagram of the sewage monitoring system. It consists of power supply unit, various sensors such as Ultrasonic sensor, gas sensor, Flow sensor, Temperature sensor, a set of LEDs, Buzzer, Liquid Crystal Display, Microcontroller ESP32 and the data is communicated through Wi-Fi connection.

Fig.1 Block diagram of the existing system

Fig.2 Schematic Diagram of the Smart Sewage Monitoring System

- The proposed solution uses an ultrasonic sensor paired with cloud software to send alerts while also documenting and storing all the necessary data for future use and data analysis.
- We use the ultrasonic sensor to keep track of the sewage level in the man-hole through the TCP/UDP platform (cloud service).
- Ultrasonic sensor monitors data and every time the level goes above a certain level of height, the system sends out an alert to the TCP/UDP platform through a mobile app or email-based alerts.

- By using water flow, gas, ph and temperature sensors we can detect flow rate of sewage and any poisonous gas present along with pH in the man hole accordingly with the temperature.
- Additionally, a buzzer is being incorporated so that a sound effective system is built in case of an the overflow of sewage water or any poisonous gas detected or temperature of the man hole is higher than the threshold.
- The proposed system monitors the level of sewage in the man –hole detects a fast leakage or flooding detection and help us to take up quick response and actions.
- Low-cost, real-time monitoring and overflow detection with alerts is one of the key features of our project which is very much necessary in the present day.
- An additional concept that is being planned to be introduced in the project is that the system detects the release of poisonous gases from the man-holes at different locations.

A. Methodology:

- The ultrasonic sensor continuously measures the distance from the top of the manhole to the sewage level. When the distance measured falls below the 7cm threshold, indicating the sewage level has risen, the sensor sends this data to a TCP/UDP server.
- Data transmitted to the server is represented in percentage form, indicating the sewage level, and is accompanied by a unique device identifier (template-id) and network details (template-SSID).
- The TCP/UDP app, configured with threshold settings, receives the data and compares it against the preset thresholds. If the sewage level exceeds the set threshold, the app triggers an alert, activating both a visual LED indicator and a notification.
- In parallel, gas and temperature sensors monitor conditions within the manhole. If poisonous gas or abnormal temperatures are detected, notifications are sent to the app for immediate action.
- Additional sensors, such as water flow and pH sensors, contribute to the monitoring process by providing real-time data on flow rates and sewage acidity, enhancing overall situational awareness.
- For heightened safety measures, a buzzer is integrated into the system to emit a loud sound in critical situations, such as sewage overflow, gas detection, or abnormal temperature levels.
- The placement of the kit, usually on the side of the manhole, ensures easy access for maintenance and monitoring. This comprehensive monitoring and alert system enables efficient management of sewage systems, promoting timely interventions to prevent hazards and maintain environmental safety.

B. Working Principle

Fig.2 shows the schematic diagram of the Smart Sewage Monitoring system which works on various stages mentioned below.

Stage 1: It consists of a Power Supply Unit (PSU) which supplies the needed power ESP 32, Ultrasonic Sensor, Gas Sensor, Temperature Sensor, Flow Sensor, ph sensor, LCD display, Buzzer and LED.

Stage 2: The ESP 32 is connected to the Power Supply Unit, Ultrasonic Sensor, Gas Sensor, Temperature Sensor, Flow Sensor, ph sensor, LCD display, Buzzer and LED and TCP/UDP app through the TCP/UDP server.

Stage 3: The Ultrasonic Sensor used detects the level of sewage inside the man hole and when it reaches the threshold level, initiates the Esp32 to send an alert notification with the relevant data to TCP/UDP app, meanwhile the LED starts blinking.

Stage 4: The Gas Sensor used checks for any gas leakages like methane, carbon monoxide etc. Poisonous gases and initiates the ESP 32 where it sends an alert notification to the TCP/UDP app.

Stage 5: The Temperature Sensor used detects temperature of the sewage water inside the man hole and initiates the ESP 32 to send an alert with relevant data regarding the temperature to the TCP/UDP app.

Stage 6: The Flow Sensor and pH sensor used detects flow rate and pH of the sewage water inside the manhole sending the relevant data to TCP/UDP app through initiating the ESP 32. As per the schematic diagram various sensors with its model name for the measurement of parameters is shown in Fig. 3.

C. Methodology

- The ultrasonic sensor continuously measures the distance from the top of the manhole to the sewage level. When the distance measured falls below the 7cm threshold, indicating the sewage level has risen, the sensor sends this data to a TCP/UDP server.
- Data transmitted to the server is represented in percentage form, indicating the sewage level, and is accompanied by a unique device identifier (template-id) and network details (template-SSID).
- The TCP/UDP app, configured with threshold settings, receives the data and compares it against the preset thresholds. If the sewage level exceeds the set threshold, the app triggers an alert, activating both a visual LED indicator and a notification.
- TCP/IP AT Commands on ESP32.
- ESP32 as a TCP client in single connection
- ESP32 as a TCP server in multiple connections
- UDP transmission with fixed remote IP address and port
- UDP transmission with changeable remote IP address and port
- ESP32 as an SSL client in single connection
- ESP32 as an SSL server in multiple connections

- ESP32 as an SSL client to create a single connection with mutual authentication
- ESP32 as an SSL server to create multiple connections with mutual authentication
- UART Wi-Fi passthrough transmission when the ESP32 works as a TCP client in single connection
- UART Wi-Fi passthrough transmission when the ESP32 works as a TCP server
- UART Wi-Fi passthrough transmission when the ESP32 works as a softAP in UDP transparent transmission
- ESP32 obtains socket data in passive receiving mode
- In parallel, gas and temperature sensors monitor conditions within the manhole. If poisonous gas or abnormal temperatures are detected, notifications are sent to the app for immediate action.
- Additional sensors, such as water flow and pH sensors as shown in fig.3, contribute to the monitoring process by providing real-time data on flow rates and sewage acidity, enhancing overall situational awareness.
- For heightened safety measures, a buzzer is integrated into the system to emit a loud sound in critical situations, such as sewage overflow, gas detection, or abnormal temperature levels.
- The placement of the kit, usually on the side of the manhole, ensures easy access for maintenance and monitoring. This comprehensive monitoring and alert system enables efficient management of sewage systems, promoting timely interventions to prevent hazards and maintain environmental safety.

D. Hardware components

- ESP32 is a single 2.4 GHz Wi-Fi-and-Bluetooth combo chip designed with the TSMC low-power 40 nm technology. It is designed to achieve the best power and RF performance, showing robustness, versatility and reliability in a wide variety of applications and power scenarios.
- The ESP32 is a series of low-cost, low-power system-on-chip (SoC) microcontrollers developed by Espressif Systems. It's widely used in IoT (Internet of Things) projects due to its versatility, built-in Wi-Fi and Bluetooth capabilities, and relatively low.
- A multi power supply board is a device used in electronic circuits to provide multiple power sources to different components or modules. These boards typically feature several output channels, each capable of delivering a specific voltage and current rating. They're commonly used in prototyping, testing, and powering various electronic projects where multiple voltage levels are required.
- A buck converter (step-down converter) is a DC-to-DC power converter that steps down voltage (while stepping up current) from its input (supply) to its output (load).
- This is an LM2596 DC-DC buck converter step-down power module with high-precision potentiometer for adjusting output voltage, capable of driving a load up to 3A with high efficiency.
- A 12V DC adapter is a power supply unit that converts alternating current (AC) from a wall outlet into direct current (DC) with a constant voltage output of 12 volts. These adapters are commonly used to power various electronic devices such as routers, modems, LED strips, CCTV cameras, and many other gadgets and appliances that require a 12V power source.
- Ultrasonic Sensor – HC-SR04: Ultrasonic sensors are devices that generate or sense ultrasound energy. They can be divided into three broad categories: transmitters, receivers, and transceivers. Transmitters (T) convert electrical signals into ultrasound, receivers(R) convert received ultrasound into electrical signals, and transceivers can both transmit and receive ultrasound.
- GAS SENSOR (MQ-2) This is a robust sensor used for sensing LPG, Smoke, Alcohol, Propane, Hydrogen, Methane and carbon Monoxide concentrations in air. If you are planning on creating an indoor air quality monitoring system; breath checker or early fire detection system, MQ2 Gas Sensor Module is a great choice. MQ2 is one of the commonly used gas sensors in MQ sensor series. It is a Metal Oxide Semiconductor (MOS) type Gas Sensor also known as Chemi-resistors as the detection is based upon change of resistance of the sensing material when the Gas comes in contact with the material. Using a simple voltage divider network, concentrations of gas can be detected.
- MQ2 Gas sensor works on 5V DC and draws around 800mW. It can detect LPG, Smoke, Alcohol, Propane, Hydrogen, Methane and Carbon Monoxide concentrations anywhere from 200 to 10000ppm.
- Water flow sensor consists of a plastic valve from which water can pass. A water rotor along with a Hall Effect sensor is present the sense and measure the water flow.
- When water flows through the valve it rotates the rotor. By this, the change can be observed in the speed of the motor. This change is calculated as output as a pulse signal by the Hall Effect sensor. Thus, the rate of flow of water can be measured.
- Temperature Sensor - DS18B20:The DS18B20 digital thermometer provides 9-bit to12-bit Celsius temperature measurements and has an alarm function with nonvolatile user-programmable upper and lower trigger points. The DS18B20 communicates over a 1-Wire bus that by definition requires only one data line (and ground) for communication with a central microprocessor. In addition, the DS18B20 can derive power directly from the data line (“parasite power”), eliminating the need for an external power supply. Each DS18B20 has a unique 64-bit serial code, which allows multiple DS18B20s to function on the same 1-Wire bus. Thus, it is simple to use one microprocessor to control many DS18B20s distributed over a large area. Applications that can benefit from this feature include HVAC environmental controls, temperature monitoring systems inside buildings, equipment, or machinery, and process monitoring and control systems.
- pH sensor **RC- A-353** is calibrated @ 24-degree centigrade room temperature. Calibrated values are:PH4-1.5V,PH7-2.0V PH9-2.5V. Place the PH Sensor probe vertically and keep it for long time before using it. Will give excellent results if the sensor probe is used multiple times in the period of 2 to 3 days. Rinse the sensor probes tube in deionised water and dab it with the tissue paper before immersing it in the test solution.

Fig. 3 The sensors used in the system with the name of the make and model

III. SOFTWARE IMPLEMENTATION

A. Flow Chart:

- The below flowchart shown in fig.4 gives the flow of working of the designed system. Once all the Hardware components are initialized in system each sensor start measuring the input sensed signals.
- The Ultrasonic Sensors used to detect the level of sewage water, if the sewage water level exceeds the preset value it sends an alert message and the Red LED starts blinking with a short duration beep sound through buzzer.
 - ❖ The present value for this prototype is 7cm (This can be programmed up to 400cm).
- The ph sensor detects the concentration of hydrogen ions present in the sewage water where the data is collected and LCD displays relevant information as per the code.
 - ❖ Ph level < 7 – water is Strongly Acidic.
 - ❖ Ph level > 7 – water is Strongly Basic.
 - ❖ Ph level = 7 – water is Neutral.

Fig. 4 Flowchart representation of the Smart Sewage Monitoring System

- The water flow sensor detects the flow of sewage water where the data is collected and LCD displays relevant information. The water flow is measured in Litre/min.
- The Temperature Sensors used to detect the temperature inside the manhole, if the temperature exceeds 35 degree Celsius it sends an alert message to the authorized person.
- The Gas Sensors used to detect the poisonous gas present in the manhole, if preset value exceeds 500 gas sensors start detects and sends an alert message.

B. ESP32 Wi-Fi Controller Application

Fig. 5 Signal flow process of ESP32 Wi-Fi Controller Application

- The ultrasonic sensor continuously measures the distance from the top of the manhole to the sewage level. When the distance measured falls below the 7 cm threshold, (this can be programmed up to 400cm) indicating the sewage level has risen, the sensor sends this data to a TCP/UDP server as shown in fig. 5.
- Data transmitted to the application is represented in numerical form, indicating the sewage level, and is accompanied by a unique device identifier (template-id) and network details (template-SSID).
- The ESP32 Dev Board microcontroller, configured with threshold settings by programming, receives the data and compares it against the preset thresholds. If the sewage level exceeds the set threshold, it triggers an alert, activating both a visual LED indicator and a notification.
- In parallel, gas and temperature sensors monitor conditions within the manhole. If the temperature exceeds 35 degree Celsius, the microcontroller sends an alert message to the TCP/UDP mobile application. If the preset gas value exceeds 500, the microcontroller sends an alert message for immediate action.

C. Arduino IDE:

- Arduino IDE is used to program the board which is a common software used for all boards belonged to the Arduino family.
- This open-source software makes it easy to write code and upload it to the board.
- It runs on Windows, Mac OS X, and Linux.

- Arduino IDE contains a text editor for writing code, a message area, a text console, a toolbar with buttons for common functions and a series of menus. It connects to the Arduino hardware to upload programs and communicate with them.
- The code is written in a simple programming language similar to C and C++.

D. Results and Discussions:

The designed system is working in all real time situations. The output readings are observed as shown in the below fig. 6 and recorded in the below table as shown in the below table 1 by the sensors for various pH levels.

Fig. 6 The various results obtained by all the sensors used

- The Ph sensor - RC-A-353 records values for acidic medium (1.26) , Neutral medium (7.02) and basic medium (10.89) which indicates that our system is efficient enough to measure all 3 aspects of pH.
- The Temperature sensor - DS18B20 used in our system has capability to measure temperature values between -55°C to 125°C. Temperature sensor sends an alert if the sewage water temperature exceeds 35 °C and the readings are shown in the table. The negative temperature is not demonstrated as sewage water is usually above the room temperature.
- The Gas Sensor – MQ2 used in this project has been set to the threshold of 500 and if the sensor encounters any gas Presence above the threshold value an alert is being initiated.
- The Ultrasonic sensor – HC-SR04 has been programmed to measure the sewage level and the preset limit is set to 7cm from the lid so that it sends an alert of rising sewage level. The threshold value is programmable upto 400 cm.
- The Flow sensor – YF – S201 measures the flow rate of the sewage in L/min and various readings are tabulated. Flow rate and the level of the sewage are interrelated and are inversely proportional to each other. When Flow rate decreases the level of sewage increases.
- Notifications of the real time results are obtained in the mobile app as per the results displayed on LCD which has shown in the fig.7.

TABLE I
THE OBSERVATIONS OF THE SENSORS FOR VARIOUS PH LEVELS

pH	Temperature (°C)	Gas Value	Level (cm)	Flow Rate (L/min)
1.26	27.25	0	5	0 [Blockage Detected]
7.02	28.50	0	15	7
10.89	49.60 [High Temperature Detected]	2906 [Poisonous Gas Detected]	8	2

Fig. 7 Notifications of the results from various sensors

IV. ADVANTAGES

- **Real-time monitoring:** The system provides real-time data on sewage levels, gas presence, pH and temperature, allowing authorities to promptly respond to any abnormalities or emergencies.
- **Early detection of issues:** By continuously monitoring sewage levels and conditions, the system can quickly detect leaks, floods, or the release of poisonous gases, enabling proactive maintenance and intervention before larger problems occur.
- **Cost-effectiveness:** The use of low-cost sensors and IoT technology makes the system economically viable for deployment in various locations. Early detection and preventive maintenance can also help save costs associated with emergency repairs and clean-up efforts.
- **Remote monitoring and management:** The central control system allows for remote monitoring of sewage systems, enabling authorities to access real-time data receive alerts from anywhere, facilitating quick decision-making and response.
- **Enhanced environmental protection:** By monitoring pH levels and flow rates, the system can contribute to maintaining water quality and environmental integrity, supporting sustainable urban development practices.
- **User-friendly interface:** LED indicators, buzzer alerts, and a centralized control system provide an intuitive interface for monitoring and managing sewage systems, making it easier for authorities to operate and maintain the system effectively.

V. LIMITATIONS

- **Maintenance:** Like any technology, IoT devices require regular maintenance and updates to ensure proper functioning. Regular maintenance checks and repairs may be needed, adding to the operational costs.
- **Data Privacy and Security:** Collecting and transmitting sensitive data about sewage levels, gas presence, and water quality raises concerns about privacy and security. Unauthorized access to this data could compromise public safety or be exploited for malicious purposes.
- **Limited Coverage:** While the prototype system may work well in controlled environments or pilot projects, scaling it up to cover an entire city or region presents challenges. Geographic factors, such as terrain, infrastructure layout, and population density, may affect the system's coverage and effectiveness.

VI. FUTURE SCOPE

- **Remote Control and Automation:** Develop capabilities for remote control and automation of sewage system operations based on real-time data analysis. This could include automatically adjusting sewage flow rates or diverting flows in case of detected abnormalities.
- **Integration with Urban Planning Systems:** Collaborate with urban planning authorities to integrate the smart sewage management system data into urban planning processes. This can help in making informed decisions regarding infrastructure development, land use, and emergency response planning.
- **Detection of sewage leakage with location indication:** An alert message sent to the concerned authority indicating sewage leakage at the location by providing the location through GPS.
- **Blockchain for Data Security and Transparency:** Implement blockchain technology to ensure the security and integrity of the data collected from various sensors. This can also enhance transparency by allowing stakeholders to access immutable records of sewage system operations.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

- Our smart city prototype for sewage management represents a significant step towards ensuring sustainable and hygienic urban environments.
- By harnessing the power of IoT technology and real-time monitoring, we have developed a system capable of detecting sewage levels, leaks, floods, poisonous gases, and abnormal temperatures, pH promptly.
- The implementation of low-cost sensors and TCP/UDP servers allows for seamless data transmission to a central control system, enabling authorities to monitor sewage systems remotely and take immediate action in case of abnormalities.
- Additionally, the incorporation of threshold-based alerts, LED indicators, and a buzzer ensures that potential issues are addressed promptly, minimizing the risk of public health hazards.
- By enhancing situational awareness and facilitating proactive interventions, our prototype system contributes to the development of smarter, safer, and more resilient cities.

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